

Analysis of Crystallisation Data for BMPR1B/FKBP12 bound to M4K2009.

XX03BMPR1BA-x001

The data was downloaded from Diamond following automatic processing using Xia2 software which suggested:

Space Group: p1 21 1

Unit cell: A = 49.15, B=184.10 C=59.42, $\alpha=90$ $\beta=104.69$ $\gamma=90$.

Resolution limit of 2.34 at $I/\sigma(I) = 2$

Completeness of 100.00 overall.

'At a glance' data output and analysis from iSpyB Diamond interface software for the first crystal.

The data looks good and it looks like the position of the crystal within the beam was good and didn't drop out of the beam during collection.

XX03BMPR1BA-x002 was also shot and a data set collected but it looks like it rotated out of the beam during the shoot so this data set was not used.

'At a glance' data output and analysis from iSpyB Diamond interface software for the second crystal.

Data analysis.

Aimless and Pointless were run as part of Diamond's automatic processing (log files attached to zenodo post).

Phasing was done using Phaser MR in the CCP4 suite of programs. The PDB file used as a model for this was 3MDY which was of the same protein complex (BMPR1B with FKBP12) bound to LDN-193189. The model used had only one chain of BMPR1B and FKBP12 present, while all ligands and waters were removed.

The Matthews coefficient suggested two complexes were present in the asymmetric unit, and this was supported after phasing was complete.

For estimated molecular weight 50134.

Nmol/asym Matthews Coeff %solvent P(2.10) P(tot)

1	5.19	76.30	0.00	0.01
2	2.59	52.60	0.98	0.97
3	1.73	28.91	0.02	0.02
4	1.30	5.21	0.00	0.00

Refinement was done using phenix refine while model fitting was done using COOT. During model refinement it was discovered that cacodylate had reacted with six cys residues (3 per BMPR1B chain). Two modifications presented themselves as being possible outcomes of this reaction:

Two possible modifications to the cysteine side chain by cacodylate proposed

The first retaining a double bonded oxygen, and the second removing it. Both reactions would necessitate catalysis by neighbouring residues. Consultation with a chemist at the SGC suggested that the former reaction was most likely however fitting of the density suggested that the latter option fitted the data better. Both modifications were present in other structures within the PDB.

Currently the latter option (with no oxygen bound to the As atom) is present within the model.

Modelling was done using the 'replace residue' function in COOT using the pre-defined three letter code CAS.

Right: Residues Cys 414 and Cys 462 modified with cacodylate and surrounding amino acids. Density shown at 2rmsd on a 2FOFCWT PH2FOFCWT map.

Left: Residue Cys 313 modified with cacodylate and surrounding amino acids. Density shown at a contour level of 2 rmsd on a 2FOFCWT PH2FOFCWT map.

After several rounds of refinement the model has the following statistics:

All-Atom Contacts	Clashscore, all atoms:	8.31	97 th percentile* (N=351, 2.340Å ± 0.25Å)	
	Clashscore is the number of serious steric overlaps (> 0.4 Å) per 1000 atoms.			
Protein Geometry	Poor rotamers	6	0.83%	Goal: <0.3%
	Favored rotamers	674	93.61%	Goal: >98%
	Ramachandran outliers	0	0.00%	Goal: <0.05%
	Ramachandran favored	785	96.08%	Goal: >98%
	MolProbity score [†]	1.73	97 th percentile* (N=8616, 2.340Å ± 0.25Å)	
	C β deviations >0.25Å	0	0.00%	Goal: 0
Peptide Omegas	Bad bonds:	1 / 6853	0.01%	Goal: 0%
	Bad angles:	0 / 9232	0.00%	Goal: <0.1%
	Cis Prolines:	0 / 38	0.00%	Expected: ≤1 per chain, or ≤5%

In the two column results, the left column gives the raw count, right column gives the percentage.

* 100th percentile is the best among structures of comparable resolution; 0th percentile is the worst. For clashscore the comparative set of structures was selected in 2004, for MolProbity score in 2006.

† MolProbity score combines the clashscore, rotamer, and Ramachandran evaluations into a single score, normalized to be on the same scale as X-ray resolution.

Molprobity analysis of model

The outstanding bad bond is on the join between a CAS modified cysteine and the neighbouring residue which the refinement software appears to be having trouble with. There are no outlying Ramachandran angles however there are fewer favoured rotamers than is ideal.

Ligand fitting of the M4K2009 compound looks good, with clear density confirming the arrangement of the ligand.

Compound M4K2009 shown bound to BMPR1B and surrounding density at a contour level of 2 rmsd on a 2FOFCWT PH2FOFCWT map.

Log files can be found attached to this zenodo page however this structure is not yet fully refined and full coordinates will be deposited in the PDB at that point.